

Factors affecting Health Insurance Purchase Decisions among the Millennials Generations

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Abstract

Health is the best wealth one can have. A healthy population is viewed as an asset for a growing & developing economy. The main objective of the paper is to study the relationship between the various factor affecting health insurance purchase decisions among the Millennials Generations using PERVAINCONSA model. The model consists of 4 components i.e., Consumer's 'Value Perception/Trust' Purchase Intention' Confidence' and 'Satisfaction'. The study is a combination of empirical and theoretical research design. The conceptual framework is framed to show the linkages among constructs; it is established based on literature reviewed and the data will be analysed & the hypothesis will be tested using Smart – PLS Software. The data were collected from 400 respondents by applying survey methods. The results of the study show a positive significant relationship between Millennial Generations Purchase intention, value, confidence and Satisfaction towards health insurance purchase decision. The finding of the study also supports some consumer behaviour theories like Theory of Planned Behaviour, Expectancy-Value Theory etc. This research will help the insurance companies to create and structure their insurance plans & policies. It will help to boost policy development, increase customer confidence and build a strong & modified pricing structures which will suit the requirements of the customer.

Keywords: Health Insurance, Millennial Generation, Purchase Decision, PERVAINCONSA model

Introduction

Health is the best wealth one can have. A healthy population is viewed as an asset for a growing & developing economy. The global forums like G20, SDGs also have the goal like “shaping an interconnection world” Considering health as an important pillar for Global growth of a country. Important SDGs related to health targets to ensure good health & wellbeing, ensuring healthy living and promoting the wellbeing of people from all age groups ([Good health and well-being - The Global Goals, 2024](#))

As it is rightly said by Ralph Waldo Emerson “Health is Wealth,” we as a concerned human being should give our 100% to protect our wealth i.e., health. Every one of us in our life Experience Unexpected events like, medical emergencies, injuries, illness that requires urgent medical treatment. We cannot always shield or guard ourselves from such events. We cannot assume that by taking care of ourselves we will always stay fit and healthy. Some situations demand immediate treatment which sometime might be costly. But we can secure ourselves financially from such situation by adhering to suitable health insurance policies. Getting oneself and our beloved one insured with a suitable policy can be considered very beneficial. It will help people to get rid of financial as well as Mental burden. There are numerous policies provided by the State and Central Government to improve quality & cashless health care services to its citizens and secure them financially during health-related emergencies ([Panda, S. 2022](#)).

Along with the government, Private players, i.e., private insurance companies also provide a diverse area of health insurance services to their customers; The private companies are gaining good reputation in the insurance business with few companies claiming 96% claim settlement ratio ([Puranik, I. A. 2025](#)).

Health Insurance

According to Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority of India (IRDAI) the term 'Health Insurance' refers to the type of insurance that basically covers your health care and medical related expenses'. It is considered as a legal contract between two parties i.e. insured and Insurer. The insurer are the employees (in case of ESIC) or Insurance companies and Insured are the Policy holders. The contract states that the insurance companies have to cover certain medical relate expenditure of the policy holder in return the policy holder has to pay premium for the coverage. The aim of health insurance is to provide financial support during medical emergencies and help in reducing out of the pocket expenditure of the policy holder and Catastrophic health expenditure.

Graph 1: The graph shows the total people across India during the period 2016 to 2023 who were covered under health insurance policy.

Source: *Statista reports*

The report here states that majority of the people are covered under government sponsored health care scheme and a very low percentage of people are covered by individual business insurance (*Statista Report, 2023*). A government sponsored insurance scheme are those health care insurance policies financed by a Central government or the State government of the specific country. The main aim of such these schemes is to offer cost-effective insurance to all the people, in a different stratum of society. On the other hand, an individual insurance plan is a plan that an individual buy without the help of any Employer and state or central government. They purchase it from their own fund considering individual or family health condition or requirement.

NITI Aayog in their report 'The Missing Middle' they stated that the Middlemen i.e. those who are not so rich to afford health insurance easily and not so poor to get government benefit are the people who constitute the major segment of uninsured segment. They are either not willing to purchase insurance or unaware about health insurance scheme. (*Report by Niti AAYOG 2021*) Studies stated that affordability and high complexities in the policies makes it difficult for the buyers leading lower purchase of health insurance (*JAMA Health Forum, 2023*). As per the Health care customer expenditure survey 2021, the customers are not very much happy/satisfied with the services providers and the health insurer (*Gordon, D. 2021*). As per the report by ACKO people are aware about health insurance policies but awareness still does not lead to purchase of health insurance. The report shows awareness level is 96% but only 43 % are owns any insurance (*Acko, T. 2025*) few studies stated that medical inflation is one reason which increases the premium rate of policies which ultimately leads to lower purchase of health insurance. Considering the Reports and Literature Reviews a study is being conducted to understand the various factors which affect the Purchase or Non-purchase of health insurance. The focus of the paper is to analyse the data using PERVAINCONSA Model, The PERVAINCONSA Model aim is to justify an Instrument which is designed to measure Consumer's 'Value Perception/Trust' 'Purchase Intention'

'Confidence' & 'Satisfaction' while taking a purchase decision. SEM using Smart PLS software will be used to check and examine the relationship established between the constructs. The main aim of the paper is to study the relationship & influence of various factor upon health insurance purchase decision using the PERVAINCONSA model (García. S. et.al 2022, Rondon-Eusebio, et.al. 2022).

Literature Review

Good Health encourages wellbeing & development of humankind (Buse et.al, 2023). Health Insurance is very crucial in protecting an individual & their families by looking after their unforeseen medical expenditure. Health insurance to a very large extent mitigates financial risk associated with health and medical expenditure, (Frankovic & Kuhn, 2023). Even after so much growth and development in insurance industry the voluntary purchase of health insurance remains low.

In the recent years Insurance sector in India has experienced a substantial growth and to a great extent the credit goes to our government and insurance regulators of the country. Globally India stands at the 10th largest in insurance market based on Premium values but as per Market research its going to be in 6th position by the year 2032 (Haris, M. 2025).

Health insurance is in very niche stage. studies suggests that there is a need to understand and explore individual factor that led to enrol in or drop out of insurance programme. Human psychology has a massive role in purchasing health insurance. Perceived intentions like perceived usefulness and perceive risk has an important role to determine purchase behaviour of a customer (Ahlin.T, et al ,2016, Brahmana, R. et al 2018).

As per some government reports and various studies around 90% of Indian citizen are uninsured mostly in under developed & rural areas, niche communities and lower-income segments. There exists a vast opportunity for health insurance companies to grow and expand if they rightly implement strategies and understand consumer need & requirement. Having proper health insurance Awareness & knowledge, developing suitable policies matching with consumer requirement which can attracts more consumer and establishing proper channel of distribution by adopting innovative technology- to carter the requirement & needs of people across the country then insurance business can go a long way and bridge the gap between among companies and uninsured people. The following Literature reviews shows theoretical and empirical studies and hypothesis building.

Purchase Intention:

Purchase intention is stated as the inclination among the customer to purchase certain product or services (Mirabi, V., et.al. 2015). Marketing a product or service focusing on consumer purchase intention basically leads to increase in purchase decision (Gazley, A., et.al. 2015). Purchase decision is a very tough and complex process. It is highly influenced by decision making style. As per the economic theory, a Rational a customer decides to purchase an item considering their experience, preferences & external environment and the availability of resources (Zhang, X., & Dong, F. 2020). Some authors consider Purchase intention approximate to purchase decision or purchase behaviour. But Without purchase intention an individual cannot make a purchase decision (Riaz, M. U., et al.2021). Purchase intention means the probability to purchase which lately associate with the actual act of purchase (Chen, Y. S., & Chang, C. H. 2012, Hamed & Halim 2005). The intention plays a crucial role as a positive intention can boost the sales and increase purchase of a product or services, and vice versa (Maithili, R. 2018, Panigrahi, S.2018). There are many factors family, friends, social and cultural factor which positively affect consumer purchase intention (Han, M. C., & Kim, Y., 2018 Kian, T. P., et.al 2017). Along with that other influencing factor of purchase intention, are individual cognition, emotion, attitude, subjective norm, perceived behaviour control and all of this have a significant positive influence over the purchase intention

of a consumer (*Prakash and Pathak 2017*). But the present study wants to find the significant relationship among the two construct i.e. Purchase intention and Health insurance purchase decision. So, the first hypotheses framed is

H01: There is no significant Positive Relationship between Purchase intention and health insurance purchase decision

Perception of Value:

Perceived value means how a customer evaluates a product or services on the basis of their merit and its ability to meet their expectation and need. It's shows how a person thinks and perceives the value & benefit of a product & service considering all essential factors.it is the driving force behind consumer purchase (*Antony, J., et al. 2023*).

As per the perceived value theory given by (*Zeithaml et.al 2020, Sweeney & Soutar 2001*) a consumer acquires the true value of product or services only when prior benefit as compared to the benefit value sacrificed by the. In order to purchase Health insurance also customer aspect immense benefit from the policy as compared to the monetary value surrendered by them.

The insurance must be satisfactory to foster its sale as the customer aspects monetary and psychological benefit. To purchase or repurchase the ultimate customer must get the desired value (*Nguyen, H. T. et al, 2023*). The present study attempts to check how consumer purchase decision of Health insurance is affected by the Perceived values of the Millennials generations.

H0 2: there is no significant Positive relationship between perceived value and health insurance purchase decision of a consumer.

Consumer Satisfaction:

As per Phillip Kotler consumer satisfaction means when the product or services meets customer expectation then it can be said that the customer is satisfied.

Few studies stated that customer satisfaction is considered as one among the strong determinant of consumer purchase or repurchase intention (*Kuo, Y. F et.al. 2009, Han kim & Hyun 2011*). When a customer is satisfied, they will again repurchase the product and services along with the motivates family and friends to do the same (*Kuo et.al 2009*).

As per consumer value theory consumer satisfaction is consequences of consumer perceived value gain about the expected value. Customer Satisfaction is widely proved as predictor of repurchase behaviour. It is solely responsible for further consumer purchase behaviour & buying decision (*Fitzgerald. 2016, Rotileanu 2021*). Based on the extensive literature, the hypotheses framed is as follows,

H03: There is no significant Positive relationship between consumer satisfaction and health insurance purchase decision.

Confidence/ Trust

Trust of a consumer means the confidence that a consumer has towards the company and its products relying on the experience, feedback and positive lookout and behaviour of the seller (*Marathe, A et.al 2014*). Trust/ Confidence in the company and its product and services is a very essential tool for the steady growth and success of an organisation. For an insurance company it's quite difficult to gain consumer trust by providing quality service (*Eid, R. 2013*). Today people are becoming conscious towards their health as well as financial health. With the growth of medical inflation, it suitable to get oneself insured with a suitable health insurance policy.

It is very essential for an insurance for an insurance company to gain consumer confidence and understand various essential factor that influence consumer to purchase or repurchase health insurance.it is essential for an insurance company because the insurance market is growing and the companies can accelerate and uplifting it business by gaining customer confidence/ trust by providing best quality service to the customer (Hero, J.O et. al 2019). Researcher stated that insurance purchase decision is highly influenced by consumer faith in the insurance company and insurer, insurer credibility helps the consumer to gain confidence in them & their policy (Ulbinaitė et.al 2013, Kiwanuka & Sibindi 2023).

An individual's confidence in insurance products significantly have positive influence over individuals purchase of personal health care products. Trust and Confidence in our service provider and regulator, had a significant positive influence over consumers involvement in insurance market. The more the level of trust the more they are willing to purchase insurance as trust enhances consumer loyalty and help to establish a strong relationship between consumer and organisation providing required services (Agyei et al. 2019, Dewi, C. S. 2023). several studies stated that brand trust is one of the best predictors of health insurance purchase decisions (Singh, A., & Shah, D. 2024. Rizwan, S. et al 2021). Going through the literature reviews extensively a hypothesis was framed to explore the relationship between consumer confidence and health insurance purchase decision.

H04: There is no significant Positive relationship between consumer confidence and health insurance purchase decision.

Theoretical Framework

A social psychologist developed a theory named The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) which is widely used in Humanities and social science research to the understanding individual behaviours which also includes including health behaviours (Ajzen, 1988, 1991). the theory is extended from a renowned and widely used theory i.e. the Theory of Reasoned Action. The TPB theory details how the individual determination influences the decision of an individual to follow and adopt a particular behaviour and take decision. As per TPB individual intention influence individual Purchase decision making (Giampietro, E. et.al 2018, Khan, Y. et.al,2023).

Individual intention represents the motivation of an individual; it's the conscious plan and effort of an individual to adopt and perform a particular behaviour. As per TPB Intention is influence by subjective norms, Attitude and Perceived behavioural Control (Conner, M., & Armitage, C. J. 1998, Conner, M. 2020). The TPB model is considered as an optimal model for measuring factors influencing consumer intentions and behaviour, it explains human behaviour and also help in predicting consumer purchase behaviour (Paul, J. et.al 2016, Liobikien'e, et.al 2016, Tommasetti, A., et.al 2018)

The theory of Consumption Value (TCV) it's a marketing theory which states that consumers' consumption behaviour or consumer choice is highly influenced by a consumer consumption values (Sheth, J. N., et.al,1991, Tanrikulu, C. 2021). The theory revolves around the idea that for the success of a service or product, it must offer some desired value to its customer. The theory highlights the significance of understanding and strengthens the perceived value for customers as a tool to achieve Competitive edge and long-term business success.

As per Expectancy-Value Theory consumer behaviour and choice is highly influenced by their belief and value they expect to derive from the product or service. People are more interested to be engaged in such activities when the probability of success is high, or the outcome is much desirable or valuable

(Drew, C. 2023). The value and expectancy attach to a product or service highly motivates individual to make a decision. (Yue, Y., & Lu, J. 2022).

As per the Expectation–Confirmation Theory a Repurchase decision of an individual is affected by their Pre Purchase Expectations its actual use and satisfaction or dissatisfaction after using the product or services. Measuring satisfaction accurately is important as companies can predict consumer behaviour and then take up necessary steps to improve consumer-satisfaction status.

Consumers Expectation Confirmation Theory (ECT) states that expectation of a consumer along with the perceived performance of the product or services leads toward satisfaction of the consumer. (Baharum, A., & Jaafar, A. 2015). Individual Satisfaction leads to future purchase intentions and actual purchase decision.

Fig 1: Conceptual Framework of The Study

Research Methodology

The study is a combination of empirical and theoretical research design. empirical research observes a phenomenon to measure reality generate knowledge and generate truth about the world by collecting and analysing data (Bhattacharya, 2008). A theoretical research design is a systematic plan used to develop, analyse, and refine theories, Model or Conceptual frameworks and provide a thoughtful insight to the research.

The present study is based on primary data collected via structured questionnaires, composed to study the 4 components of PERVAINCONSA Model (García-Salirrosas, E. E., & Acevedo-Duque, Á. 2022). Purchase decision is a very long process. There must be an intent to purchase then only an individual can make an actual purchase decision (Riaz, M. U., et al.2021) along with the consumer trust, confidence in the company and various product is also very important. 5- Point Licker Scale of measurement has been adopted to measure the respondent's reaction towards purchase of health insurance based on the various factors stated. A pilot study was conducted with 40 respondents which were selected randomly and reliability and validity of the data and items wear measured.

Data Collection: Data were collected from a particular age group 28 years to 43 popularly known as the millennial's generations from Northeast India. Millennials, the largest living generation. The earning generation and the perfect age to take up health insurance as the premium will be bit lower. At this age this generation people are mostly well settled, employed and started a family or going to start a family. This is an appropriate age to get insured as they are going to interact with the medical Responsibilities health care expenditure for themselves and family independently for the first time in their lives. so, to secure their future financially from health-related burden taking health insurance ius the right decision (Arensberg, L. C., et al 2022). As the study focused on Millennial generation and their population is more than 100,000, so as per Das, et al. 2016 to achieve 95% level of confidence in the study the minimum considerable sample size should be 400. So, in the present study data were collected from 400

respondents randomly through google form and survey method. Out of 400 hundred only 327 responds were complete and correctly filled so this 327 is considered as the sample size.

Data Analysis: The fig: no 1 shows the conceptual framework of the study. The framework shows the relationship between the constructs and hypothesis that will be tested using Smart PLS 4.09, along with that SPSS will be used to check reliability and validity. SEM through SmartPLS gives a significant insight to the strength and help to build direction of relationships among the constructs, it assists the researcher to properly understand how various factors will influence customer purchase decision. (Hair, et al., 2011, Uddin, et al., 2023, Rahman, & Rahman, 2023)

A Pilot study was conducted using 40 samples. According to Connelly (2008), The reliable sample size for a pilot study should be 10% of the sample size planned for the main study. The researcher conducted a pilot study by taking 40 samples which is more than 10% of 400 (400 = Planned sample size for the main study).

Reliability And Validity

Table no. 1 Reliability Statistics

Reliability o		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	Number of Items (N)
.844	.871	28

Source: IBM SPSS

Reliability is the test to measure the consistency and stability of the data collected during the research. It measures the internal consistency of the data and shows how much the finding is reliable. It shows how much the finding of the research can be trusted and replicated. The common method used for reliability testing is measuring through Cronbach alpha value using SPSS. A commonly used threshold value for Cronbach alpha value (α) is above 0.70. Here, the Cronbach alpha value (α) is 0.844. This confirms the reliability of the construct.

Table no.2 shows the validity of data using KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.865
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Sig	.000

Source: IBM SPSS

The researcher has applied construct validity test with the help of KMO and Barlett test of Sphericity. An adequate value of KMO should be in between 0.8 to 1. KMO value less the 0.6 means the sample is not adequate. In case of Barlett test of Sphericity the P value should be less than 0.05. As shown in table no.2 KMO value is 0.865 (adequate) and Barlett test of Sphericity is less than 0.05 so its also significant. So, as per the pilot study the data set and questionnaire are valid and reliable.

PLS-SEM Analysis

To study the effect of independent variables that are ‘Value Perception/Trust’ ‘Purchase Intention’ ‘Confidence’ and ‘Satisfaction’ on dependent variable i.e., health insurance Purchase decision making; PLS SEM is applied. The two parts of the PLS-SEM causal modelling approach are evaluation of the measurement model (outer model) and evaluation of the structural model (inner model) (Hair, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2011). The Null hypothesis framed are:

H₀1: There is no significant Relationship between Purchase intention and health insurance purchase decision

H₀2: There is no significant Relationship between Perceived value and health insurance purchase decision

H₀3: There is no significant Relationship between confidence and health insurance purchase decision

H₀4: There is no significant Relationship between Satisfaction and health insurance purchase decision.

Assessment of Measurement Model/ Outer Model

The first part of Partial Least square SEM is assessment of the measurement model which basically calculates the reliability and validity. Reliability is measured to check the consistency & trustworthiness of a measuring scale. The Cronbach alpha value was used to measure internal consistency and to identify the reliability of the items. A commonly used threshold value for Cronbach alpha value (α) is above 0.70. Average Variance Extracted value and Composite Reliability value is used to evaluate the validity of the measurement model (Hair, Sarstedt, Hopkins, & Kuppelwieser, 2014).

Graph no 2: PLS- SEM Algorithm

Source: SmartPLS V 4.9

The path diagram is used to show the relationship between variables. The above graph shows the effect and presence of relationship between the variables. The graph is followed by a calculation of reliability and validity of the model.

Table no 3: Reliability & Validity using Cronbach’s alpha, Composite reliability(rho_c) & Average Variance Extracted (AVE). (N = 327).

	Factor Loading	Cronbach’s alpha	Composite reliability(rho_a)	Composite reliability(rho_c)	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Purchase intention	PI1-0.779 PI2-0.915 PI3-0.810	0.920	0.923	0.938	0.719

	PI4-0.933 PI5-0.734 PI6-0.896				
Perceived value	PV1-0.774 PV2-0.838 PV3-0.852 PV4-0.776 PV5-0.434	0.789	0.804	0.861	0.563
Confidence	C1-0.782 C2-0.951 C3-0.796 C4-0.860 C5-0.889 C6-0.896	0.931	0.937	0.946	0.747
Satisfaction	S1-0.675 S2-0.775 S3-0.848 S4-0.811 S5-0.595 S6-0.685	0.868	0.882	0.900	0.601
Purchase Decision	PD1-0.481 PD2-0.870 PD3-0.858 PD4-0.736 PD5-0.835	0.920	0.860	0.875	0.593

Source: SmartPLS V 4.9

As per the above table no.3 the Cronbach’s alpha value of all the variables exceeded the recommended value of 0.70 which confirms the reliability of the construct. The minimum acceptable value of Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and CR are 0.50 and 0.70 respectively. As per the table Composite Reliability of all the construct is above 0.7 and AVE exceeds 0.5 which conforms validity of the construct (Hair, J. F, 2017)

Divergent Validity

Divergent validity is used to show that the measure of constructs is not theoretically highly not correlated to each other (Hubley, 2014). Through Heterotrait- Monotrait ratio criterion, the Divergent validity can be measured on the basis that all the values must be less than 0.85 (< 0.85). The values between the variables are less than 0.85 which means there is presence of divergent validity. In simple words, variables are not practically and theoretically correlated with each other (Henseler, et al. 2009).

Table no. 4 Results of Heterotrait- Monotrait ratio

	Confidence	Perceived value	Purchase Decision	Purchase intention	Satisfaction
Confidence					
Perceived value	0.606				
Purchase Decision	0.722	0.527			
Purchase Intention	0.808	0.515	0.609		
Satisfaction	0.668	0.797	0.766	0.804	

Source: SmartPLS V 4.9

As per shown in Table no. 4 it can be clearly concluded that all the values of HTMT Ratios are as per the requirement i.e. less than 0.85, therefore the threshold level indicates satisfactory discriminant validity.

Assessment of Structural Model/ Inner Model

Structural equation model (SEM) helps to explore that relationship among exogenous and endogenous latent constructs by evaluating coefficient of determination i.e., R2 value and β value, that is, "path coefficients "of the model (Chin, 1998). To study the model fit i.e. of any model constructed by an researcher, they must check the "goodness of fit" the most common measures used by the researcher are "Standardized root mean squared residual" (SRMR), "Normed fit index" (NFI), and "R-square" (R2), the goodness of fit to evaluate the model.

Table no 5. Model evaluation with R-squared

	R-squared	R-squared Adjusted
Purchase decision	0.773	0.763

Source- SmartPLS V 4.9

R-squared (R²): It is the test to show how much one independent variable explains the dependent variable in a models fit. Higher is the value of R² stronger is the relationship between variables (Gupta, A. et.al 2024). The minimum recommended R² value is that it should explain 10% of the variance to justify the explanatory power of a model fit (Falk & Miller, 1992).

Here, the value of R² is 0.773 i.e. which is adequate and shows 77% of variance in the dependent variable is explained by the 4 independent variables of the study.

Table. no 6. Model fit

	Saturate Model	Estimated model
SRMR	0.063	0.063
d_ ULS	5.147	5.147
d_ G	4.156	4.156
Chi-square	550.159	550.159
NFI	0.554	0.554

Source- SmartPLS V 4.9

As per the Model fit Indices the values obtained from SRMR, d_ ULS, d_ G, Chi-square test, and Normed fit index (NFI) the value of saturated Model is compared with the estimated model and based on that it shows a good Model fitness. The maximum threshold of SRMR is 0.08 and in the respective model as shown in the table no. 6, the SRMR value is 0.063, below the maximum threshold of 0.08. As a result, the value shows a good model fit (Hair, et al., 2019).

Path Coefficients

The path coefficient is used to show the result of hypothesis testing by evaluating the P Value. It helps to show the hypothetical relationship among the constructs.

Table 7: Results of Path Coefficient

Hypothesis	Relationship	Original sample (O)	Sample mean(M)	Standard deviation	t-value	p-value	Result
H1	Purchase intention ->		0.517	0.088	5.958		Rejected
H2	Purchase Decision	0.524	0.395	0.056	7.089	0.000	Rejected
H3	Perceived value -> Purchase	0.397	0.904	0.114	7.918	0.000	Rejected
H4	Decision	0.903	0.514	0.061	8.442	0.000	Rejected
	Confidence -> Purchase	0.515				0.000	
	Decision						
	Satisfaction -> Purchase						
	Decision						

(Source- SmartPLS V 4)

The path coefficient should be between -1 and + 1 for the relationships established in the study using Measurement and Structural model. (*Hair, Ringle & Sarstedt, 2011*).

Findings

The finding of the study supports the Theory of planned behaviour as it states that Intention influence decision making process. The study also found that individual purchase intention has significant relationship with purchase decision and influence purchase decision. The table shows the result of hypothesis tested using PLS-SEM. The test result of first hypothesis shows the P. Value for H01 is 0.00 which is less than 0.05. if the P. Value is less than 0.05 then the null hypothesis is Rejected ($p < 0.05$) (*Hair et al., 2014*). Hence the first hypothesis is Rejected, which ultimately means there exist a significant relationship between purchases intention and healthy insurance purchase decision. The findings are supported by previous studies like (*Dapas, C. C et.al 2019, Satriawan, K. A.et al 2020, Aliza, N. A. S. E. E. M. 2012*).

The finding of the study also supports Theory of consumption value & Expectancy-Value Theory as it states individual decision to purchase highly depends on the value they expect to derive from the product or services. The study also proves that individual purchase decision has significant relation with perceived value. Second hypothesis of the study shows that there is no significant relationship between perceived value and health insurance purchase decision of a consumer which is also rejected as the P. Value is again less than 0.05. which shows there exist a significant relationship between perceived value of a customer and their health insurance purchase decision (*Hoo, D. Z. 2021, Abdelfattah, F. A., et.al.2015*). The finding of the study also supports Expectation–Confirmation Theory as the theory states Individual Satisfaction leads to future purchase intentions and actual purchase decision. Here, H04 shows a that there exists a relationship between purchase decision and customer Satisfaction. This study's third hypothesis (H3) is that consumer confidence on Company & Product have no significant relationship with health insurance purchase decision of a consumer and the hypothesis was Rejected, As The p- value less 0.05. The finding of the study also supports previous research studies (*Fitzgerald. 2016, Rotileanu 2021*). Similarly, the 4th hypothesis was also rejected, which proves that there exists a significant relationship among Consumer Satisfaction and health insurance purchase decision. (*Sudirjo, F., & Sulistiyani, S. 2023*). As per the path analysis, it was found that Consumer's 'Value Perception/Trust' 'Purchase Intention' 'Confidence' and 'Satisfaction' has significant relationship with health insurance purchase decision.

Conclusion

Health insurance is at its nascent stage in India. With the growth of medical inflation and growing diseases there is an urgent need of every individual to get yourself insured. So, that they can easily mitigate their

health-related financial burden. There are various factors which influences an individual to purchase an insurance, the Present study attempts to show the relationship between the various factors driving health insurance purchase among the Millennials. As per the result of the study found, it can be concluded that the four important variables of PERVAINCONSA Scale i.e. Value Perception/Trust' 'Purchase Intention' 'Confidence' and 'Satisfaction' shows a significant relationship with health insurance purchase decision, as all the hypothesis framed were rejected. Adequate service provided by a company helps to increase consumers' confidence in the product or services and helps to boost the purchase of health insurance. Insurance companies can derive useful information from the present research finding. It is essential for an insurance company to gaining customer confidence/ trust by providing best quality service to the customer. This can help to boost the overall growth of insurance business. Their perception towards the product & company also plays a significant role. The insurance must be satisfactory enough to foster its sale as the customer aspects monetary and psychological benefit. To purchase or repurchase the ultimate customer must get the desired value they are expecting to derive. As per the consumer purchase intention also have significant relationship with purchase decision. Marketing a product or service focusing on consumer purchase intention specially the millennials then it can lead to increase in purchase of health insurance. They are the bread earning generation and are in the most suitable age group to purchase insurance as the premium will be much lower. As a result, it can be stated that these 4 Variable i.e. Value Perception/Trust' Purchase Intention' Confidence' and 'Satisfaction' are the factors which have significant impact on purchase of health insurance. But the factors are not limited to these 4 there are many factors which influence purchase decisions which are not studies in this paper. For further research some other factors like individual factors, consumer perceived factors, organisational factors can be studied. This research will help the insurance companies to create and structure their plans and policies. It will help to boost policy development, increase customer confidence and build a strong & modified pricing structures which will suit the need of the customer. The finding might assist the government and regulators in formulation of regulations that support greater access to health insurance with the objective to improve the financial security of the people.

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